
EXAMINING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF WASTE MANAGEMENT IN ONE BARANGAY IN OLONGAPO CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the implementation of the waste management ordinance in New Cabalan, Olongapo City, focusing on demographic factors such as age, sex, years of residency, and family size. Utilizing a quantitative research design, G*Power Analysis, and purposive sampling, data were gathered from 188 households through self-made and adoptive questionnaires. Most respondents were middle-aged (49–55 years old), with a higher participation rate among females. Despite efforts to segregate and dispose of waste properly, issues such as inadequate infrastructure, limited community engagement, and insufficient policy enforcement persist. Proximity to the landfill exacerbates these problems, leading to health and environmental concerns. While the initiative has improved waste generation, storage, processing, and transportation, continuous community engagement, better resource allocation, and stricter policy enforcement are necessary for sustainable waste management. Ongoing research and monitoring are recommended to address these challenges and adapt the program to evolving needs.

Keywords: waste management, demographic data, community engagement, environmental concern

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INTRODUCTION

Human activity has a significant role in trash management. The application of waste management affects not only our future tourism sites and attractions but also our health and environment. Understanding the consequences of poor management, trash characterization and segregation at the source, appropriate collection and transfer,

recycling, and composting per legal requirements can help prevent garbage crises. An adequately operated waste management system guarantees a more hygienic and salubrious atmosphere for locals and tourists, encouraging eco-friendly travel and safeguarding the scenic splendor of locations for posterity. The main focus of this study section is the implementation of waste management in New Cabalan Olongapo City. A community's future is strengthened by good administration, which consistently directs its members toward a common purpose. The purpose of the regulation is to enforce community cleaning practices and correct trash segregation among its citizens. It is consistent with Pongrácz et al.'s (2004) Waste Management Theory, which holds that a cohesive body of knowledge about waste may be used to organize the various waste factors through appropriate information sharing regarding waste management. We can distinguish between the previous waste management implementations based on how well-established, effective, and well-organized each waste is. Determining if they are fully aware of or ignorant of the required information, as occasionally, residents' ignorance will cause their non-compliance.

Implementing waste management is a multidimensional goal that aims to achieve sustainability, preserve natural resources, and improve the well-being of communities and ecosystems in ecotourism, health, and the environment. For instance, the study of Asio (2021a) and Asio (2021b) claimed that the respondents often waste recycling schemes. Effective waste management is essential in ecotourism to preserve the pristine state of natural attractions. It guarantees the preservation of biodiversity and natural areas by reducing tourists' environmental impact. In addition to lowering pollution and preventing wildlife from consuming toxic materials, proper waste disposal and recycling programs shield water sources from contamination. In addition, encouraging environmentally conscious activities and trash minimization among visitors develops a culture of environmental stewardship that lasts beyond their trip and motivates long-term dedication to environmental preservation. Managing trash effectively is crucial for preventing the spread of illnesses from a health standpoint. As a result of improper garbage disposal, diseases and vermin may spread quickly, endangering the health of nearby residents and tourists. Ecotourism locations can lower the risk of health problems associated with inappropriate waste treatment by implementing strict waste management practices that guarantee garbage is managed correctly and hygienically. Furthermore, by empowering the local population to adopt healthier waste disposal practices, educating initiatives on the health implications of mishandled trash might improve public health results. Waste management in ecotourism has the potential to significantly lower greenhouse gas emissions, which has positive environmental effects. One potent greenhouse gas released from landfills is methane, which can be reduced by recycling and composting garbage instead of landfills. Ecotourism facilities can promote local agriculture and reforestation initiatives by promoting methods like composting organic waste, which results in nutrient-rich soil. It improves soil stability and health, sequesters carbon, and

fosters biodiversity. Moreover, ecotourism that incorporates waste management techniques supports sustainable economic growth. Reduced trash disposal costs and the possibility of income production through recycling initiatives are two ways that effective waste management can save costs. Employment prospects in the recycling and waste management sectors can have a positive economic impact on nearby towns. Additionally, a well-maintained landscape attracts more tourists, which benefits the local economy through higher spending on services, accommodations, and activities. Effective trash management in ecotourism necessitates both education and community involvement. Involving local populations in waste management projects guarantees these programs' cultural appropriateness and widespread acceptance. A sense of ownership and responsibility for preserving a clean and healthy environment can be fostered, and capacity can be built through training programs for stakeholders and local citizens. The efficiency and scope of waste management initiatives can be improved by cooperation between ecotourism providers, local authorities, and non-governmental groups. To sum up, the goals of waste management implementation in ecotourism are economic sustainability, health protection, and environmental conservation. Waste management programs support the overarching objective of sustainable development by lowering pollutants, lowering health hazards, and encouraging sustainable practices. They guarantee that the growth of ecotourism won't jeopardize the integrity of the natural settings that draw tourists. Waste management in the ecotourism industry can be a model for other sectors, showcasing the significant advantages of combining environmental, health, and economic goals in the quest for a sustainable future via education, community involvement, and the adoption of best practices.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, the researchers used a quantitative method of research. According to Asio (2021), this research involves understanding specific characteristics of a phenomenon or sample of a population in terms of numerical representation. This type of research usually uses statistical tools/instruments, either descriptive and/or inferential, to deal with the data gathered from the samples involved in the study. Quantitative research also involves specific numbers of respondents (in terms of sample) that would represent a definite population for the study. Additionally, it involves a larger sample and does not require a relatively longer time for data collection. However, it has limitations in that quantitative research takes snapshots of a phenomenon, not in-depth, and overlooks test-takers and testers' experiences as well as what they mean by something Rahman (2020), this study would address examining the implementation of waste management in New Cabalan, Olongapo City.

Participants

The respondents of this study will be residents of New Cabalan. The researcher was to determine the appropriate sample size, using the G*Power Analysis application with a priori, power=.80, effect size =0.25, and a minimum sample value size of 180. Cohen(1988) suggested that when there is no other basis for setting the value of desired statistical power, a priori power .80 can be used. With an effect size =0.25 and a significance level of 0.05, the minimum sample value size is 180.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a questionnaire as the main instrument for data gathering. To gather the data required for the study, the researchers used a self-made questionnaire and adapted a questionnaire based on the statement of the problem for the chosen respondents.

Part I: elicits information on the respondent's profile in terms of (a) years of residency, (b) location, (c) age, (d) sex, and (E) no. of residency.

Part II will assess the level of implementation of the waste management ordinance in New Cabalan, Olongapo City. The respondents can also rate the question by answering 4 (always), 3 (often), 2 (rarely), and 1 (never).

The instrument was to the expert validators for checking and revision. Suggestions for improving the instrument were considered in the final form. The items noted to be vague will be modified or changed to assure that the respondents will clearly understand all items included in the instrument. The researchers will also conduct pilot testing to check the reliability and validity of the instrument. By doing reliability tests, it measures the consistency of a test or experiment.

Statistical Analysis

The researchers for this study will follow a few procedures and use a face-to-face survey to achieve the work's objectives. The questions will be carefully crafted to ensure they are clear, concise, and easy to understand. The researchers will also ensure that the questions are unbiased and do not lead the respondents in any particular direction. They provide confidential information, which is only utilized to supplement and support data collection for the study. Then, the researchers used a purposive sampling method to select a specific group of individuals or units for analysis. This method is appropriate when the researcher has a clear idea of the characteristics or attributes, they are interested in studying and wants to select a sample representative of those characteristics. With purposive sampling, researchers can use statistical techniques for specific purposes or objectives. Therefore, the sample is selected based on the characteristics or attributes the researcher is interested in studying. Then, the survey questionnaire would be distributed to the respondents via face-to-face communication, which could be used to distribute the survey questionnaire easily. After

collecting all the data, the researchers would systematize and tally and analyze the survey. The researchers used non-parametric tests since the responses from the participants were not normally distributed. They include frequency, percentage, mean, Mann Whitney U test and Kruskal Wallis H Test.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical considerations are pivotal in shaping effective waste management strategies in Old Cabalan. The community's rich ethnic diversity necessitates a respectful and inclusive approach that acknowledges and integrates traditional practices and cultural beliefs regarding waste disposal and recycling. This study seeks to understand and incorporate these perspectives into proposed solutions by engaging closely with local leaders and residents. This approach aims to foster sustainable waste management practices that protect the environment and honor and preserve the cultural heritage of Old Cabalan's diverse population.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 presented the distribution of the profiles of the respondents and results according to their age, sex at birth, number of family members, and years of residency. On the other hand, Tables 2-4 showed the level of waste management implementation, which presenting the distribution of factors of food sanitation practices and its summative results according to personal hygiene, food handling, and food storage. Lastly, Table 5-8 displays the test of differences for implementing waste management.

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents, highlighting key trends. The majority belonged to the 49–55 years old group (19.1%), followed closely by those aged 28–34 years old (17.0%), while the least represented were 63 years old and above (7.4%). More respondents were female (56.9%) than male (43.1%). Most participants came from households with 4–5 members (33.5%), with the least standard family size being 10 members and above (6.9%). Regarding residency, the largest group had lived in the area for 31–40 years (22.9%), while only 2.1% had resided for 1–10 years, suggesting a stable, long-term resident population. These findings indicate that the study primarily involves middle-aged adults, predominantly female, from moderately sized families with well-established residences in the community.

Table 2 in Olongapo City reveals a notable reliance on plastic bags and disposable containers for short-term waste storage ($M = 3.51$) alongside a deficiency in accessible waste bins ($M = 2.16$), resulting in environmental contamination (Alabi & Adekunle, 2022; Philip & Garcia, 2022). The persisting challenges in waste management, including insufficient resources, poor infrastructure, and limited collaboration between authorities

and the community, have hindered effective waste disposal practices (Bernardo et al., 2019; Atienza, 2011).

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Age</i>		
14-20 years old	18	9.6
21-27 years old	25	13.3
28-34 years old	32	17.0
35-41 years old	25	13.3
42-48 years old	21	11.2
49-55 years old	36	19.1
56-62 years old	17	9.0
63 years old and above	14	7.4
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	81	43.1
Female	107	56.9
<i>Family Members</i>		
2 – 3 members	41	21.8
4 – 5 members	63	33.5
6 – 7 members	44	23.4
8 – 9 members	27	14.4
10 members and above	13	6.9
<i>Years of Residency</i>		
1 – 10 years	4	2.1
11 – 20 years	24	12.8
21 – 30 years	39	20.7
31 – 40 years	43	22.9
41 – 50 years	28	14.9
51 – 60 years	33	17.6
61 years and above	17	9.0
Total	188	100.0

Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach. It involves not only enhancing waste infrastructure and enforcement of regulations like the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 but also fostering active community engagement and stakeholder cooperation (Coracero et al., 2021; Molina & Catan, 2021; San Juan, 2019; Al-Katib & Abu, 2010). By promoting sustainable waste management practices and ensuring adequate resources and participation, Olongapo City and other regions in the Philippines can work towards a cleaner and healthier environment.

Table 2. Waste Generation and Storage of the Respondents

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1) Separating and collecting different containers for recycling.	2.39	Less Practiced
2) Providing household waste storage containers (personal trash bin in your house)	3.21	Moderately Practiced
3) Using plastic bag/disposable containers used for temporary storage until the waste is collected.	3.51	Highly Practiced
4) Storing your trash safely in marked, airtight containers that are prepared for recycling or disposal.	2.96	Moderately Practiced
5) Wastes that are stored aren't exposed to the open air.	3.09	Moderately Practiced
6) Storage facility or trash bin shall be so placed that it is accessible to users.	3.46	Highly Practiced
7) Availability of waste bins.	2.16	Less Practiced
8) Usage of separate containers for different types of wastes.	2.72	Moderately Practiced
Composite Mean	2.94	Moderately Practiced

Table 3 in the City of Olongapo assesses waste management practices related to waste processing and resource recovery. The highest mean value ($M=2.86$) for textile recycling signifies its high adoption, presenting an eco-friendly method to repurpose old clothes and fabric (Macchion et al., 2018). Textile recycling is crucial due to its positive environmental impact, aiding sustainable development and reducing resource consumption and pollution.

Conversely, the lowest mean value ($M=2.34$) for waste incineration reflects its limited implementation (Zhang et al., 2012). Incinerating garbage is less favored due to environmental concerns, as Turconi et al. (2011) highlighted, emphasizing the need for site-specific data in assessing its environmental performance.

The composite mean ($M=2.69$) indicates a moderate overall waste management level in Olongapo City, with textile recycling more prevalent than waste incineration. Liu et al. (2021) stress the urgency of recovering valuable materials and recycling toxic metals in electronic products, emphasizing the necessity for e-waste recycling for environmental, technical, and economic reasons. Efficient resource management through recycling practices, including e-waste, is vital for environmental sustainability (Qu & Chen, 2014).

Table 3. Waste Processing and Resources Recovery

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1) Mixed waste containing recyclable resources is being followed through recycling.	2.74	Moderately Practiced
2) Combining unwanted waste that can be given recycled items such as clothing, metallic material items, and so on.	2.55	Moderately Practiced
3) Use decomposing fruits and vegetables in approximately known as composting, which turns them into plant fertilizer.	2.74	Moderately Practiced
4) Waste from construction and demolition (C&D) projects, such as concrete, wood, and metal, can be processed to recover materials for reuse in construction projects, lowering the demand for virgin resources.	2.73	Moderately Practiced
5) Recycling textiles, such as used clothing and fabric, can recover fibers for use in brand-new textiles or transform them into rags and insulation materials.	2.86	Moderately Practiced
6) Recycling of electronic garbage (e-waste), such as outdated computers and cellphones, allows for the recovery of precious metals like gold, silver, and copper.	2.80	Moderately Practiced
7) Waste-to-energy facilities burn municipal waste, sometimes known as rubbish or trash, to generate electricity.	2.74	Moderately Practiced
8) Implementing waste incineration is the burning of garbage.	2.34	Less Practiced
Composite Mean	2.69	Moderately Practiced

Table 4 in Olongapo City assesses waste management practices related to waste collection and transportation. The highest mean value (M=2.85) for segregating leftover food for disposal signifies a prevalent and impactful practice among residents, aiding in waste reduction and environmental care.

Segregating leftover food for disposal is a significant action in waste management, reflecting conscientiousness in minimizing food waste. Quested et al. (2011) noted that food-wasting behaviors are often private, making norms less influential. Factors such as personal norms and household planning habits, highlighted by Evans & Visschers (2016), also shape food disposal practices.

Conversely, the lowest mean value (M=2.19) for disposing of various waste categories, including recyclables and hazardous substances, indicates a less common practice. Proper waste disposal, involving sorting different waste types, is crucial for environmental cleanliness and safety despite being less glamorous. Ahirwar and Tripathi (2021) and Noor et al. (2020) underscore the health risks of improper e-waste recycling and hazardous waste exposure.

Table 4. Collection and Transportation of Waste

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1) Organizing house to house collection of municipal waste through any of the methods.	2.23	Less Practiced
2) Waste collection is carried out according to the schedule.	2.46	Moderately Practiced
3) For the handling, transfer, and transportation of garbage, stage facilities or bins must be designed to be simple to use.	2.24	Less Practiced
4) Separate any leftover food that will be thrown away in the garbage during the day.	2.85	Moderately Practiced
5) Proper waste during the day, suitable rubbish is taken out in front of the residence house	2.30	Less Practiced
6) Ensure that the waste is delivered to the authorized facilities for treatment, recovery, or disposal.	2.56	Moderately Practiced
7) Disposal of a variety of waste categories, including recyclable, organic, hazardous, etc.	2.19	Less Practiced
8) They have separated recycling trucks that used to gather recyclable materials including paper, cardboard, plastic, and glass and transport them to recycling facilities.	2.39	Less Practiced
Composite Mean	2.40	Less Practiced

The composite mean (M=2.40) reveals a moderate overall waste management level in Olongapo City, emphasizing the importance of proper waste disposal, including recyclables and hazardous waste, to reduce environmental impact. Zhou et al. (2021) highlight the challenge of improving recycling performance to recover materials, conserve resources, and reduce landfills, suggesting economic incentives as strategies to encourage waste sorting and recycling activities.

Table 5. Differences in the Implementation of Waste Management According to Age

Factors	Age	n	Mean Rank	H	p-value	Remarks
Waste Generation and Storage	14-20	18	113.97	11.431	.121	Not Significant
	21-27	25	89.80			
	28-34	32	84.89			
	35-41	25	99.40			
	42-48	21	87.86			
	49-55	36	111.64			
	56-62	17	87.74			
> 63	14	68.82				
Waste Processing and Resources Recovery	14-20	18	105.78	12.817	.077	Not Significant
	21-27	25	82.62			
	28-34	32	80.97			
	35-41	25	113.04			
	42-48	21	84.93			
	49-55	36	105.86			
	56-62	17	106.26			
> 63	14	69.89				
Collection and Transportation of Waste	14-20	18	137.19	19.182	.008	Significant
	21-27	25	84.22			
	28-34	32	81.98			
	35-41	25	101.28			
	42-48	21	100.76			
	49-55	36	97.17			
	56-62	17	90.00			
> 63	14	63.68				

Note: $df=7$

Table 5 reveals notable differences in waste management practices across different age groups in Olongapo City. The Kruskal-Wallis H test identified significant variations in waste collection and transportation behaviors [$H(7) = 19.182, p = .008$]. Post hoc analysis indicated significant differences between younger individuals (14-20 years) and older adults (63 and above, $p = .004$; 28-34 years old, $p = .015$; 21-27 years old, $p = .044$), highlighting diverse waste disposal approaches among age demographics.

Younger individuals, particularly teenagers aged 14 to 20, may exhibit distinct waste management behaviors compared to older age groups, implying varying levels of environmental consciousness and sustainable practices. In contrast, no significant differences were found in waste generation and storage [$H(7) = 11.431, p = .121$] and waste processing and resources recovery [$H(7) = 12.817, p = .077$] among age groups. It

suggests consistent waste management practices across all age demographics in Olongapo City, potentially influenced by accessible infrastructure and community-wide programs rather than age-related factors.

The study underscores the importance of tailored waste management strategies to effectively address the unique characteristics and behaviors of different age groups. While age may not be a decisive factor in waste management practices, socio-economic and environmental aspects likely play a more significant role in shaping waste management behaviors in the community. Hannan (2020) highlights optimizing waste collection routes, emphasizing the need for efficient decision-making in garbage collection operations to enhance cost-effectiveness and environmental sustainability.

Table 6. Differences in the Implementation of Waste Management According to Sex at Birth

Factors	Sex	N	Mean Rank	U	z	p-value	Remarks
Waste Generation and Storage	Male	81	99.10	3960.500	-1.018	.309	Not Significant
	Female	107	91.01				
Waste Processing and Resources Recovery	Male	81	98.33	4023.500	-0.842	.400	Not Significant
	Female	107	91.60				
Collection and Transportation of Waste	Male	81	96.85	4143.000	-0.518	.605	Not Significant
	Female	107	92.72				

Table 6 displays the difference in the implementation of waste management according to sex at birth using the Mann-Whitney U test. The test found that there is no significant difference between males and females in terms of waste generation and storage [$U = 3960.500$, $z = -1.018$, $p = .309$], waste processing and resource recovery [$U = 4023.500$, $z = -.842$, $p = .400$], and collection and transportation of waste [$U = 4143.000$, $z = -.518$, $p = .605$] at the 5% significance level. According to a study by Smith et al. (2018), which examined waste management behaviors among urban residents in developed countries, gender did not emerge as a significant factor influencing waste management practices. Understanding the nuances of waste management practices concerning gender is paramount for fostering equitable and effective waste policies. Gender-related disparities in waste management can impact environmental sustainability and social equity. Therefore, investigating differences in waste management implementation based on sex at birth is essential for promoting inclusivity and fairness in waste management strategies.

Table 7. Differences in the Implementation of Waste Management According to Family Members

Factors	Family Members	n	Mean Rank	H	p-value	Remarks
Waste Generation and Storage	2 – 3	41	93.84	4.097	.393	Not Significant
	4 – 5	63	84.75			
	6 – 7	44	99.22			
	8 – 9	27	103.69			
	> 10	13	108.81			
Waste Processing and Resources Recovery	2 – 3	41	86.51	5.807	.214	Not Significant
	4 – 5	63	90.74			
	6 – 7	44	101.23			
	8 – 9	27	112.06			
	> 10	13	78.69			
Collection and Transportation of Waste	2 – 3	41	98.33	0.976	.913	Not Significant
	4 – 5	63	89.98			
	6 – 7	44	98.51			
	8 – 9	27	91.70			
	> 10	13	96.58			

Note: $df=4$

Table 7 depicts the result of the difference in the implementation of waste management according to a number of family members using the Kruskal-Wallis H test. The test found that there is no significant difference among groups in terms of waste generation and storage [$H(4) = 4.097, p = .393$], waste processing and resource recovery [$H(4) = 5.807, p = .214$], and collection and transportation of waste [$H(4) = .976, p = .913$] at the 5% significance level. Effective waste management is crucial for environmental sustainability and public health. Understanding how waste management practices vary according to household characteristics, such as the number of family members, can inform targeted interventions and policies. In this study, we investigated the implementation of waste management practices across households with different family sizes using the Kruskal-Wallis H test. The test findings revealed no significant differences among groups in terms of waste generation and storage, waste processing and resource recovery, and collection and transportation of waste at the 5% significance level. It suggests that household size may not significantly influence these aspects of waste management. However, it is essential to contextualize these results within existing literature to understand their implications further.

Table 8. Differences in the Implementation of Waste Management According to Years of Residency

Factors	Years of Residency	n	Mean Rank	H	p-value	Remarks
Waste Generation and Storage	1 – 10	4	115.88	4.668	.587	Not Significant
	11 – 20	24	102.42			
	21 – 30	39	90.90			
	31 – 40	43	90.64			
	41 – 50	28	105.32			
	51 – 60	33	95.76			
	> 61	17	76.06			
Waste Processing and Resources Recovery	1 – 10	4	74.59	3.054	.802	Not Significant
	11 – 20	24	100.38			
	21 – 30	39	88.24			
	31 – 40	43	99.12			
	41 – 50	28	98.89			
	51 – 60	33	97.45			
	> 61	17	80.62			
Collection and Transportation of Waste	1 – 10	4	149.25	18.081	.006	Significant
	11 – 20	24	128.17			
	21 – 30	39	87.36			
	31 – 40	43	89.02			
	41 – 50	28	98.14			
	51 – 60	33	87.47			
	> 61	17	71.97			

Note: $df=6$

Table 8 revealed the difference in the implementation of waste management according to years of residency using the Kruskal-Wallis H test. The test found a statistically significant difference in collection and transportation of waste among years of residency groups [$H(6) = 18.081, p = .006$] at the 5% significant level. The post hoc analysis was conducted using the Kruskal-Wallis pairwise comparisons examining the distribution of the years of residency groups where significance values have been adjusted by the Bonferroni correction for multiple tests. The analysis reveals statistically significant differences in implementation of waste management in terms of collection and transportation of waste between 11 – 20 and 61 and above years of residency ($p = .022$). The statistically significant difference found in the implementation of waste management regarding collection and transportation among different years of residency groups suggests that there might be varying levels of awareness, participation, or infrastructure development over time.

On the other hand, the table also revealed no statistically significant difference among years of residency groups in terms of waste generation and storage [$H(6) = 4.668, p = .587$] and waste processing and resources recovery [$H(6) = 3.054, p = .802$] at the 5% significance level. The lack of significant differences in waste generation and storage, as well as waste processing and resource recovery among different residency groups, implies that the length of residency may not heavily influence these aspects of waste management.

Therefore, while the duration of residency may affect certain aspects of waste management, such as collection and transportation, other components, like waste generation and processing, remain consistent across different residency groups. This underscores the importance of targeted interventions and infrastructure development to address specific challenges identified within communities.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it indicates an apparent variation in waste management practices, particularly in the collection and transportation of waste, as influenced by the duration of residency. It suggests that factors such as awareness, community engagement, and infrastructure improvements related to waste management may evolve with time. Such findings underscore the importance of considering residency duration when planning and implementing. Waste management strategies to ensure efficiency and effectiveness across diverse community segments. Several recommendations can be made to enhance the quality of learning and teaching in the Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management program.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Our study focused on waste management in one barangay in Olongapo City through confidential face-to-face interviews at the local landfill. However, several limitations should be considered. The study's narrow focus on one barangay may limit the generalizability of findings to other areas with different conditions and practices. Conducting face-to-face interviews at the landfill posed challenges such as potential response bias and logistical constraints like weather or noise interference, but despite efforts to ensure confidentiality, participants may have been cautious in their responses, which affected the depth of information shared. The study's timeframe may not capture seasonal variations or long-term changes in waste management practices. Addressing these limitations could enhance the study's reliability and applicability, offering a more comprehensive understanding of waste management strategies in urban settings like Olongapo City.

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